

REMITTANCES AND ECONOMIC GROWTH: A CASE STUDY OF PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT: In south Asia Pakistan is placed at the second number in receiving remittances after India. Remittances flows in Pakistan are second largest source after foreign direct investment (FDI). Pakistan uses its remittances to meet twenty percent of imports and matched thirty percent of exports which is healthy sign for the economy. There are twenty countries which used remittances in this way. Many studies have been done on this topic which revealed diverse results of remittances on economic growth. It sometimes positively impacts and sometimes negatively impacts economic growth of a country. There are also some studies which show neutral impact. This study analyzed short-run and long-run effect of workers' remittances (WR) along with foreign direct investment (FDI) and money supply on the Pakistan's economic growth with the help of time series data which is from 1973-2013. ARDL (Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag) of Co-integration technique is used in this study which is relatively new technique. Time span which has been used in this study is 40 years which is not previously used for Pakistan. Findings of the given study indicate that economic growth is significantly and positively impacted by remittances and foreign direct investment during short period and long period. Granger causality test is also applied and found that workers' remittances do cause economic growth while economic growth does not cause workers' remittances. For policy implication it has been recommended that Pakistan should reduce transfer cost of remittances and should develop organized channels to increase the volume of workers' remittances.

KEYWORDS: Remittances, FDI, GFCF

1. INTRODUCTION

The remittances are the incomes of those people who work in other countries. The workers go from one country to other, to earn their income. When remittances are sent within the country from one area to other are called internal remittances. On the other hand when remittances are received from different countries are called international remittances. Economic growth of any country is widely affected by the migration of the people. Usually people's migration occurred when there is lack of opportunities in the country and they are compelled to find earning in the other developed countries. Workers' remittances are important source of foreign exchange earnings in the developing countries. It has been observed that during last three decade remittances flow has been increased more than twenty times. Developing countries received remittances amounted 436 billion US dollars during 2014 which is new record of remittances for developing countries. Overall worldwide remittances volume is 583 billion US dollars (*Economic Survey of Pakistan*, 2014).

Workers' remittances appeal researchers, scholars, decision makers regarding their effect on the growth in emerging economies or developing countries. There are many studies in which different sources of growth has been discussed like new technologies, use of surplus labor, foreign direct investment, foreign aid and return on investment (Barro, 1991; Denison, 1967; Lewis, 1954; Romer, 1986; Solow, 1956). Workers' remittances are used by developing countries to reduce the gap of balance of payments. Workers' remittances are also used to support families, relatives during financial crises and natural calamities (Orozco, 2003; Ratha, 2007). Recipient countries use worker's remittances for economic growth, poverty reduction, quality education, health and investment (Calero, Bedi, & Sparrow, 2009; Faini, 2007; Gupta, Pattillo, & Wagh, 2009; Jongwanich, 2007; Stark & Lucas, 1988; Taylor, 1992).

1.1 Remittances and Economic growth

A number of studies are available which shows that foreign remittances impact the economic growth. (Feeny, Iamsiraroj, & McGillivray, 2014) analyzed that remittances are important for the economic growth of the countries. (Luqman & Haq, 2016) investigated that remittances are used to develop

financial sector of the economy which further play vital role in the economic growth of the country. There are mix opinions about workers' remittances and economic growth relationship. Due to declining share of agriculture and absence of suitable means for livelihood, many of the Pakistani workers migrate in order to get better employment opportunities, better working environments and higher wages (Ahmed, Zaman, & Shah, 2011). Remittances have their own significant importance and stable nature because these are considered different from foreign direct investment (FDI), aids and foreign credits (Kapur & Singer, 2006).

Remittances and cash arrivals are suitable only for shorter period while for longer period economic growth exports should be increased rather than workers' remittances (Waheed & Aleem, 2008). It also has been found that due to rise in remittances, poverty level declined (Anwar, 2004). International migrants from developing countries sent \$404 billion in 2013 (World Bank, 2014).

Pakistan is basically agricultural country which has real per capita GDP of \$ 1,386 along with a rising unemployment rate, which reached 6.2 percent in 2013. Pakistan confronted increased emigrant rate since the late 1970s, due to which Pakistan received massive amount of remittances and it became the largest source of foreign capital (Al Khathlan, 2012). Remittances are considered 2nd major source after FDI. Nonetheless, in second quarter of fiscal year 2014, FDI was 750.9 million dollars while remittances were \$12895 million (Economic survey of Pakistan, 2013-14). Pakistan is also part of those twenty countries where remittances cover more than 20% of export monetary value of country. In some year it covers more than 30%. Government of Pakistan wants to discover more markets where it can send its manpower and will receive more remittances.

Regarding Pakistan, many studies have been carried out by different researchers at micro and macro level. These studies focused mainly to describe the remittances' impact on economic growth and development either directly or indirectly (Adams Jr, 1998; Amjad & Ahmed, 1986; Burney & Ahmad, 1987; Kozel & Alderman, 1990; Malik, Sarwar, & Siddiqui, 1993; Nishat & Bilgrami, 1991; Nishat, Bilgrami, & Kazi, 1993). Generally, these studies explore positive influence of remittances on the economy of Pakistan like on investment, aggregate consumption. Worker remittances also helpful in covering deficit of current account and covering debt burden it is also helpful in improving health and education in country.

Therefore, the present research was designed to explore long run relationship between Worker remittances and Economic growth in Pakistan. It also discussed the short run dynamics of Worker remittances and Economic growth in Pakistan. In this study worker' remittances along with technical education, Gross Fixed Capital Formation, Employed Labour Force, Money Supply and Foreign Direct Investment has been used. Real Economic growth is used as dependent variable. In this study Granger causality test is applied to check the causation. Such model is not previously used.

This study has been organized as section 2 presents review of related literature. Section 3 discusses methodology and data which is used for this research. Section 4 entails results and discussion. Section 5 is about conclusion of the study and it also gives policy implications.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section shows the findings of selected studies which are relevant to the current research. (Salahuddin & Gow, 2015) used the panel data from 1977 to 2012 of the famous remittances recipient countries like Pakistan, India, Bangladesh and Philippines and find the results that remittances has highly significant positive impact on economic growth in long run. They also examined that short run relation is positive but it is insignificant. They used Westerlund and Panel Pedroni cointegration tests to confirm the long run relationship of remittances and economic growth.

(Luqman & Haq, 2016) used the time series of Pakistan from 1972 to 2011 and investigated that

development of financial sector of Pakistan has increased the remittances volume which is vital for economic growth. They constructed financial sector development index with the help of principal component analysis. They used ARDL bound testing technique for cointegration.

(Dahal, 2014) used the data of Nepal and examined the impact of remittances on economic growth which is positive and significant. He further explained that remittances play important role in the development of financial sector and human capital. He also observed the negative relationship of remittances with international trade while he investigated the positive association of remittances with entrepreneurship and negative with manufacturing.

(Datta & Sarkar, 2014) analyzed long run association of economic growth and remittances in Bangladesh. They used the annual data of remittances and economic growth (GDP) of Bangladesh from 1975-2011. They used the ARDL econometric technique. Further, they found no significant causal relationship of growth-remittances nexus in Bangladesh on basis of secondary data testing. They also explained that if remittances will use for conspicuous consumption or in the unproductive sector, then remittances can affect economic growth negatively.

(Dilshad, 2013) used 22 years data of Pakistan from 1991-2012 and observed the remittances impact on economic growth. He identified the relation of variables by using regression model. He calculated positive and significant relation between economic growth and remittances of Pakistan. By keeping results of his study in mind he recommended that measures should be taken to promote remittances inflow.

(Javid, Arif, & Qayyum, 2012) further dug deep relationship of remittances and growth along with taking consideration of poverty in their analysis. They used data set from 1973 to 2010 on annual basis by ARDL approach. Results of their study shows that economic growth has affected significantly and positively by remittances and remittances played vital role in reduction of poverty. Results of their study also indicate that internationally migrated labor can provide huge benefits to the poor people of Pakistan as well as the people of other developing countries. So, now it is the responsibility of government to take such measures by which remittances can be increased by abolishing the cost of transaction which incurred during transferring remittances from legal channels.

(Jawaid & Raza, 2012) analyzed through empirical studies that economic growth is positively affected by remittances. They used the data of 113 developed and underdeveloped countries for the period of seven years. Their research findings shows that remittances played more powerful role in those countries who have high income while remittances role in less income countries is not powerful.

(Siddique, Selvanathan, & Selvanathan, 2012) found the nexus between workers' remittances and economic growth in Sub continent region. They have picked three counties of Sub-Continent i.e. Sri Lanka, India and Bangladesh. Researchers unable to find causal relationship between WR and economic growth in India and Bangladesh while in Sri Lanka it was found that remittances and economic growth cause each other. They used only two variables remittances and economic growth. They used time series data of 25 years for three countries. Their findings are based upon vector Auto regression (VAR) framework and causality is tested by Granger methodology.

(Hossain, 2012) investigate the casual link between remittances, economic growth, electricity consumption and export values. He used time series data of three SAARC countries for 34 years. He applied Johanson Fisher panel co-integration and Kao tests for co-integration and find out that variables are co-integrated. He also checked the causality of economic growth and export values and he came to know that relation of variables is not casual in long run. Further, he examined that consumption of electricity and remittances elasticity in long run with economic growth is very much high in comparison of elasticity in short run which means high remittances and electricity consumption play vital role in

enhancing economic growth.

(Al Khathlan, 2012) by using the remittances and economic growth data of Pakistan from 1976 to 2010 examined the significant positive long-run & short-run relation of these variables. He further examined that remittances are considered as the key source of foreign capital inflow. He used real GDP as proxy of economic growth and Remittances as independent variable, Gross fixed capital formation, FDI, Exports, Rate of inflation as independent variable. He used (ARDL) and (ECM) techniques to find long run and short relation of his empirical model. (Irfan, 2011) analyzed through empirical study that remittances and GDP play significant role in poverty alleviation and economic growth. He used data of Pakistan from 1975 to 2009.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The model 3.1 is formulated and analyzed to explore effect of remittances on economic growth of Pakistan. Worker remittances are focal variable of the empirical study along with Gross Fixed Capital Formation, Employed Labour Force, Broad money, FDI which is net inflows of percentage of GDP and EDU (Technical & Vocational Institutions Enrollment). All variables are in log form because Solow growth model has been used which was presented in 1956 while it was further used by Weil, Romer and Mankiw in 1992.

$$(1) \quad GDP = \beta_0 GFCF^{\beta_1} L^{\beta_2} WR^{\beta_3} M2^{\beta_4} FDI^{\beta_5} TECEDU^{\beta_6} e_t$$

$$(2) \quad LGDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LGFCF_t + \beta_2 LL_t + \beta_3 LWR_t + \beta_4 LM2_t + \beta_5 LFDI_t + \beta_6 LTECEDU_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Where,

LGDP= log of GDP (Million Rupees)

LGFCF= log of Gross Fixed Capital Formation (Million Rupees)

LL= log of Employed Labour Force (Million)

LWR= log of Worker's Remittances (Million Rupees)

LM2= log of Broad money (Million Rupees)

LFDI=log of Foreign direct investment, net inflows (% of GDP)

LTECEDU= log of Enrollment in Technical Institutions (000)

ε_t = Error Term

Data set used in this study is from 1973 to 2013. Data is taken from state bank of Pakistan website and World Development Indicators (WDI). Education data is obtained from various issues of economic survey of Pakistan.

3.1 Unit Root Tests

It is conditional to check stationarity test for data series which is used in econometric model so as to evade problem of unreliable results which stem from spurious regression and this situation arises due to non-stationary of data. (Ouattara, 2004) said that for bounds testing it is necessary that data series should be integrated of order I(0) or I(1). (Pesaran, Shin, & Smith, 2001) advocated, If integration is at I(2) (on second difference) then F-statistic value will become invalid By using ratios, differences and log, a series which is non-stationary can be converted into stationary series. Stationarity of the variables can be checked by using following tests.

3.1.1 Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test

Augmented Dickey Fuller test is formulated and applied by (Dickey & Fuller, 1979) to avoid the symptoms of spurious estimation and to check the stationarity of the data. Serial correlation is

controlled by the use of higher order lag from Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF). For the solution of serial correlation problem ADF is also used for those error terms which are correlated. Null hypothesis of ADF test indicates that series is non-stationary (unit root series) while alternative hypothesis is set that series is stationary: i.e.

$$H_0 = \delta_2 = 0 = \text{unit root exist in series}$$

$$H_1 = \delta_2 = 1 = \text{series is stationary}$$

Using ADF test following equation of regression is estimated by this procedure:

$$(3) \quad \Delta W_t = \delta_0 + \delta_{1t} + \delta_{2t} + \delta_2 W_{t-1} + \sum_{k=1}^p \phi_k \Delta W_{t-k} + u_t$$

Here “q” indicates the number of lagged changes in W_t which is considered important to make error term u_t serially uncorrelated. It is assumed that error term has no heteroskedastic. There are two more tests which can also be conducted in this regard.

$$(4) \quad \Delta W_t = \delta_0 + \delta_2 W_{t-1} + \sum_{k=1}^p \phi_k \Delta W_{t-k} + u_t$$

And

$$(5) \quad \Delta W_t = \delta_2 W_{t-1} + \sum_{k=1}^p \phi_k \Delta W_{t-k} + u_t$$

Here equation (4) is used to characterize the series as I (1) have drifted and equation (5) I (1) is representation of without time trend and drift. Null hypothesis of these all tests based on existence of unit root in data while alternatives deal stationary series. Test statistics (t value) is used to check the presence and absence of unit root.

$$(6) \quad \text{Test statistics} = \frac{\hat{\delta}_2}{\text{SE}(\hat{\delta}_2)}$$

Null hypothesis will be rejected when calculated value of (t- value) test statistics is more than tabulated critical values, developed by (MacKinnon, 1990) and if calculated value is less than tabulated value then alternative hypothesis will be accepted.

(MacKinnon, 1990) devised a mechanism to accept or reject the null hypothesis of test. It reveal if calculated value of test > tabulated value, we are in favor of reject the null hypothesis of unit root existence. Nevertheless, value of test < tabulated value provide sound grounds to accept null hypothesis.

During the application of ADF test, an important issue of lag length selection arose. When there is so small lag length then serial correlation (auto correlation) will bias the empirical results of the test and when there is too large lag length selection then power of test will hurt. (Ng & Perron, 1995) presented the solution of this problem. .When the value of t-statistics is less than 1.6 then decrease the lag length by one and perform the same process.

3.1.2 Phillips-Perron Test

(Phillips & Perron, 1988) developed Phillips-Perron test which is modified and generalized form of ADF test. This test explains the automatic correction of auto correlated error term. Hypothesis and

regression equations of Phillips-Perron test are similar to ADF test (with drift and time trend and without drift and time trend). Test statistics of PP test are also same as in ADF test and test statistics (t-value) are compared with tabulated values.

3.2 Graphical Analysis

We can also judge the stationarity of the data series with the help of graph. When we plot data and see any trend in the plotted data then we can say that the data series is non-stationary. To achieve the purpose of stationary we take difference of variables until it become stationary. Normally time series data become stationary at first difference or second difference. That differenced data exclude all trend and fluctuate around its mean value.

3.3 Stability Test

CUSUM test is used to check the structural stability of parameters in short and long run while CUSUM square test is applied to quantify stability and constancy of parameters of the model. These tests are proposed by (Brown, Durbin, & Evans, 1975) and (Pesaran et al., 2001). They said that if the results of both of these test lie within 5 % level which are expressed by two straight lines then we can say that there exists significant and stable relationship among the variables.

3.4 ARDL Bounds Testing Procedure

(Pesaran & Pesaran, 1997; Pesaran et al., 2001) developed Bounds testing approach to check long run relationship which is prior step before applying ARDL (Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag) technique. To fulfill above purpose, following equations has been estimated which shows the short run and long run co integration among the variables.

$$(7) \quad \begin{aligned} \Delta LGDP_t = & \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_{1i} \Delta L(GDP_t)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{2i} \Delta L(GFCF)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{3i} \Delta L(L)_{t-i} + \\ & \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{4i} \Delta L(WR)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{5i} \Delta L(M2)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{6i} \Delta L(FDI)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{7i} \Delta L(TECEDU)_{t-i} \\ & + \delta_1 L(GDP)_{t-1} + \delta_2 L(GFCF)_{t-1} + \delta_3 L(L)_{t-1} + \delta_4 L(WR)_{t-1} + \delta_5 L(M2)_{t-1} + \delta_6 L(FDI)_{t-1} \\ & + \delta_7 L(TECEDU)_{t-1} + \mu_t \end{aligned}$$

Here L denote log of variable, GDP is proxy of economic growth and Δ represent differenced variables Where short run coefficients are denoted by α s and long run multipliers are denoted by the δ s. Optimal lag length of ARDL model is denoted by 'm'.

Below given is expression of ARDL null and alternative hypothesis

$$(8) \quad H_0 = \delta_1 = \delta_2 = \delta_3 = \delta_4 = \delta_5 = \delta_6 = \delta_7 = 0$$

$$(9) \quad H_1 = \delta_1 \neq \delta_2 \neq \delta_3 \neq \delta_4 \neq \delta_5 \neq \delta_6 \neq \delta_7 \neq 0$$

Wald Test will be used to test above hypotheses and we shall compute F-statistics by using equation (1). Further, we shall compare calculated value of F- statistics with tabulated critical values of (Pesaran et al., 2001) table. If F- statistics calculated value is greater than upper bound then we shall reject null hypotheses which indicate that there is no co-integration and we shall accept alternative hypotheses which indicate the co-integration. Null hypothesis will not be rejected if F- stat. value which is calculated is less in comparison of lower bound value. If the F- stat. value is in between the lower bound and upper bound then it indicates inconclusive results.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results of Unit root

Firstly stationarity of variables is checked before estimation of the econometric model. ADF and PP

tests are used to check the stationarity and results are verified. ADF test information can be seen from the table 1.

Table 1 Details of the results of Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test

Variables	1(0)		1(1)	
	Intercept	Trend & Intercept	Intercept	Trend & Intercept
Ln(GDP)	-0.557345	-1.846450	-4.848309*	-4.761398**
Ln(WR)	-1.195906	-1.897653	-4.342816**	-4.318091**
Ln(GFCF)	-2.340661	-5.161141*	-4.191935**	-4.568072**
Ln(L)	0.025659	-1.760377	-6.932685*	-6.841886*
Ln(M2)	-1.707931	-2.887485	-4.615153*	-4.648928**
Ln(FDI)	2.318014	-4.847741**	-5.254461*	-4.643299**
Ln(TECEDU)	0.668273	-1.695760	-6.538432*	-6.658444*

*, **, *** has been used to mention the level of significance at 01%, 05% and 10% respectively.

ADF test results in the table 1 shows, there is only gross fixed capital formation and FDI variable are stationary at level with trend and intercept while it is necessary that variable should be stationary with intercept as well as with trend and intercept so, these variables are also stationary at first difference and all other variables including GDP, Worker’s Remittances, Employed labour Force, Broad money and education are stationary at 1st difference because at level these variables are non-stationary and null hypotheses has not been rejected on the bases of t-statistics.

Similarly PP test results are mentioned in the table 2 which shows that there is not a single variable which shows stationarity at level, variables used in the model are showing stationarity at the 1st difference like GDP, gross fixed capital formation, Worker’s Remittances, Broad money, FDI and education. According to the results of both tests ADF and PP, all variables which are taken in this study are integrated of order I (0) and I (1). None of the variables is integrated of order I (2). So, ARDL methodology is ideal for such data set.

Table 2 Details of the Results of Phillips-Perron (PP) Test

Variables	1(0)		1(1)	
	Intercept	Trend & Intercept (Inclusion)	Intercept	Trend & Intercept (Inclusion)
Ln(GDP)	-0.927765	-1.816622	-4.849855*	-4.761398**
Ln(WR)	-1.155248	-2.066385	-4.342816**	-4.318091**

Ln(GFCF)	-2.500894	-4.422628**	-4.009173**	-4.394905**
Ln(L)	-0.028409	-1.961195	-6.897255*	-6.816349*
Ln(M2)	-1.534798	-2.184284	-4.615153*	-4.679689**
Ln(FDI)	-1.777599	-1.887005	-4.240558**	-4.099880**
Ln(TECEDU)	1.038541	-1.695760	-6.557918*	-6.829839*

*, **, *** has been used to mention the level of significance at 01%, 05% and 10% respectively.

4.2 Graphical Analysis

Non stationary at level

Graphical analysis of the variables $\ln(\text{GDP})$, $\ln(\text{WR})$, $\ln(\text{GFCF})$, $\ln(\text{M2})$, $\ln(\text{FDI})$, $\ln(\text{L})$ and $\ln(\text{TECEDU})$ shows that there is upward trend at level while this trend is not found at first difference. From this we reached to this conclusion that these variables are non-stationary at level while stationary at first difference.

4.3 Lag Length Selection Criteria

After checking the stationarity of the variables next bound testing approach is applied for co-integration and maximum lag length selection is done. Mostly Akaike Information and Schwarz Bayesian criterions are used for maximum lag length selection. If there is no found auto correlation by using both criterions then we shall find lag length of the model which provides the minimum critical value of Criteria. In this study Schwarz Bayesian criterion has been applied for the lag length selection. Table 3 is representation of shows the lags in Schwarz Bayesian criterion (SBC) settings and Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). These both lag criteria are widely used in ARDL methodology

Table 3 Details of Lag Selection Criteria for Model

Lags	AIC	SBC
1	-15.37094	-12.95765*
2	-16.29481	-11.76990
3	-18.02683*	-11.39029

The optimum lag length 1 has been selected because at lag one Schwarz Bayesian criterion has minimum value. According to Akaike Information criterion minimum value is at lag 3 but problem of degree of freedom will rise due to increase number of lags. The Schwarz Bayesian criterion is selected for lag order to apply ARDL bound testing approach rather than Akaike Information criterion because it has low prediction error (Ma & Jalil, 2008).

4.4 Results of ARDL Bounds Testing

To get results of long-run relationship existence among the variables, F- test is applied. Null hypothesis of this test indicate no long-run relationship among the variables while alternative hypothesis means long-run relationship exists among the variables. Following table 4 the value of F-statistic is 4.45 which is more than the upper bound value at 5% and 10% level of significance. When calculated value exceeds upper bound, we can reject null hypothesis of no long run relationship and accept alternative hypothesis that reveals existence of co-integration among variables. This finding gives proves that dependent and independent variables have statistically co-integration. This finding provide basis for applying ARDL approach.

Table 4 Details of Wald’s F-Statistic for Testing Co-integration

F-Statistics	10% significance		5% significance	
	LB I(0)	UB I(1)	LB I(0)	UB I(1)
4.45	2.08	3.00	2.39	3.48

After confirming long run relationship among variables, we move towards long run estimation of ARDL model and results of long run estimation are shown in the table 5.

$$(10) \quad \Delta L(GDP_t) = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_{1i} \Delta L(GDP_t)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{2i} \Delta L(GFCF)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{3i} \Delta L(L)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{4i} \Delta L(WR)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{5i} \Delta L(M2)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{6i} \Delta L(FDI)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{6i} \Delta L(TECEDU)_{t-i} + \mu_t$$

Table 5 Estimated Long Run Coefficients using the ARDL Approach

ARDL (1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 1) selected based on Schwarz Bayesian Criterion

**Dependent variable is Ln(GDP)
40 observations used for estimation from 1973 to 2013**

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio	Probability
Constant	-1.722883	0.583077	-2.954811**	[.006]
Ln(GFCF)	0.098169	0.116820	0.840346	[.407]
Ln(L)	2.448341	0.564633	4.336166*	[.000]
Ln(WR)	0.075235	0.025242	2.980589**	[.005]
Ln(M2)	0.513525	0.146365	3.508520*	[.001]
Ln(FDI)	0.051490	0.022199	2.319455**	[.027]
Ln(TECEDU)	.10887	.063518	1.7139***	[.097]

*And ** denotes 5% and 10% level of significance, respectively.

Long run relationship between GDP per capita, Workers’ remittances, Gross fixed capital formation, employed labour force, money supply, foreign direct investment and Technical education is shown in the above table. It is clear from the table that all variables have positive impact on GDP.

In this study, main variable (Worker Remittances) impacts GDP positively, that is also statistically significant on basis of P value of variable. Workers’ remittances’ Coefficient 1% increase will increase 0.07% economic growths of Pakistan. These results are similar to the results of the study done by (Al Khathlan, 2012) that also showed the positive effect of workers’ remittances on economic growth.

FDI has also statistically significant and positive relation with economic growth of Pakistan. It means

FDI positively affects GDP per capita. Coefficient of Foreign direct investment indicates that 1% increase in foreign direct investment will increase the economic growth of Pakistan by 0.05%. Such results are also found by (Al Khathlan, 2012).

Money supply positively and significantly affects the economic growth of Pakistan. The result of this study shows that 1% increase in money supply will increase 0.51% economic growth of Pakistan. These results are consistent with results of the study by (Ahmed et al., 2011). The results of Technical education are significant and has positive impact on economic growth of Pakistan which means 1% increase in enrollment in technical institutions will increase the economic growth of Pakistan by 0.10%. Our findings are similar to the findings of (Ahmad, Mushtaq, & Afzal, 2014; Bartel & Lichtenberg, 1987; Sharma & Gani, 2004).

Gross Fixed capital formation insignificantly and positively impact the economic growth of Pakistan. This may be due to data issue. Our results are consistent with the results of (Al Khathlan, 2012) and (Dilshad, 2013).

Employed labour force is impacting economic growth positively and significantly. The result shows that 1% increase in employed labour force will increase the economic growth of Pakistan by the value of 2.4%. As technical education enhances the skill of the labour so that is why labour is contributing more in economic growth of Pakistan. With the passage of time enrollment in technical institutions is increasing which is positive sign regarding economic growth.

Error correction model has been estimated for the short dynamic parameters on the basis of the following equation.

$$(11) \quad \Delta \ln(GDP_t) = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_{1i} \Delta \ln(GDP_t)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^m \alpha_{2i} \Delta \ln(GFCF)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^m \alpha_{3i} \Delta \ln(L)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^m \alpha_{4i} \Delta \ln(WR)_{t-i} \\ + \sum_{i=0}^m \alpha_{5i} \Delta \ln(M2)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{6i} \Delta \ln(FDI)_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{7i} \Delta \ln(TECEDU)_{t-i} + \phi(ECM)_{t-i} + v_t$$

Where ' ϕ ' is basically coefficient of ECM which is speed or pace of adjustment from short run equilibrium point toward long-run equilibrium point. Equation 12 is representation of ECM.

$$(12) \quad ECM_t = \Delta \ln(GDP)_t - \sum_{i=1}^m \alpha_{1i} \Delta \ln(GDP_t)_{t-i} - \sum_{i=0}^m \alpha_{2i} \Delta \ln(GFCF)_{t-i} - \sum_{i=0}^m \alpha_{3i} \Delta \ln(L)_{t-i} \\ - \sum_{i=0}^m \alpha_{4i} \Delta \ln(WR)_{t-i} - \sum_{i=0}^m \alpha_{5i} \Delta \ln(M2)_{t-i} - \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{6i} \Delta \ln(FDI)_{t-i} - \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha_{7i} \Delta \ln(TECEDU)_{t-i} - v_t$$

Short run adjustment has been taken place toward long-run equilibrium relationship among variables by Error Correction Model (ECM). Coefficient of ECM indicates that the model will adjust towards the long-run equilibrium from short-run disturbance by the speed of 56% per year.

R-Square value is used to analyze accuracy or fitness of the model. It provides explanatory power of the model that reveal how much variation in dependent variable is explained by set of independent variables.

Explanatory power of the model is 61% variation in economic growth of Pakistan is due the independent variables. When we adjust the model with degree of freedom output of the explanatory power is called adjusted R-square. It is net effect of explanatory power after minimizing the impact of superfluous variables or observations that is 46%. F-statistic reveals overall model fitness, calculated value of F-statistics is 4.1 and its probability value is in favor of highly significant model.

Table 6 Error Correction Representation for the Selected ARDL Model

ARDL(1,1,1,0,0,1) on based SBC				
Regressor	Coefficient	Stand. Error	T-Values	Probability
dC	-1.0001	.40795	-2.4515	[.020]
dLn(WR)	-.011390	.014088	-.80851	[.424]
dLn(GFCF)	.040376	.028285	1.4275	[.163]
dLn(M2)	.074609	.029779	2.5054	[.017]
dFDI	.0077076	.0038739	1.9897	[.055]
dLn(EDU)	.024434	.017627	1.3862	[.175]
ecm(-1)	-0.557598	0.129082	-4.319710	[.000]
R-Squared = 0.617519 Adj R-squared = 0.467259				
F-stat. $F(7, 33) = 4.109660, \text{Prob}(F\text{-stat}) = [.001]$				
Mean of Dependent Variable = .0146450				
S.D. of Dependent Variable = 0.049304				
DW value = 2.1996				

4.5 Diagnostic Tests

Accuracy, robustness and efficiency of result mainly based on diagnostic tests, to achieve this purpose I have applied Ramsey's RESET for functional form, The Lagrange multiplier (LM) test serial correlation, Skewness kurtosis of residuals for normality of residuals while White General tests for Heteroscedasticity. These tests verified that there is no Serial Correlation, Heteroscedasticity and Functional Form problem. Diagnostic tests results have been shown in the Table 7.

Table 7 Details of the Diagnostic Tests

Problem	Test	X ² -statistic	F-statistic
Serial Correlation	Lagrange Multiplier	X ² =1.3152[.251]	F=.99423[.327]
Normality	Skewness and Kurtosis of Residuals	X ² =1.4466[.485]	-----
Functional Form	Ramsey's RESET	X ² =1.4561[.228]	F=1.1046[.302]

4.6 Test of Model Stability

To check the stability of parameters, stability tests have been applied which are (CUSUM) and (CUSUM square). Following graphs proved the stability of the model in which it has been presented that the fitted lines stays within 5% critical bounds. So, the null hypothesis of the parameters is rejected and

alternative hypothesis is accepted which indicates that model is stable. Graphs show that speed of adjustment from short-run towards long-run is stable at 5% level of significance and fluctuations outside the critical bounds is not found.

Figure 1 Plot of Cumulative Sum of Recursive Residuals

Red dotted lines represent five percent level of significance in CUSUM Test.

Figure 2 Plot of Cumulative Sum of Squares of Recursive Residuals

Red dotted lines represent five percent level of significance in CUSUM Square Test.

4.7 VAR Granger Causality Test

VAR Granger Causality Test has been used to find the unidirectional, bidirectional causality of the variables of the present study. Through test it has been discovered that Worker’s remittances does cause the economic growth while GDP does not cause the workers’ remittances so in these two variables unidirectional causality is found from workers’ remittances to economic growth. Similarly causality among other variables is also checked and found that Employed labour force has unidirectional causality to economic growth. There is bidirectional causality between money supply and economic growth. Gross Fixed Capital Formation has no causality with economic growth. Technical education does cause the economic growth while economic growth does not so, there is unidirectional causality between these two variables. Economic growth cause the foreign direct investment while FDI does not have causation with economic growth again there is unidirectional causality. GFCF also cause Foreign

Direct investment while FDI does not cause GFCF.

Table 8 Details of the Results VAR Granger Causality/Wald Tests

Dependent Variables	Independent Variables						
	Ln(GDP)	Ln(GFCF)	Ln(L)	Ln(WR)	Ln(M2)	Ln(FDI)	Ln(TECEDU)
Ln(GDP)		3.21 (0.20)	17.50* (0.00)	17.56* (0.00)	7.48* (0.02)	1.49 (0.47)	7.19* (0.02)
Ln(GFCF)	2.21 (0.33)		2.00 (0.36)	0.58 (0.74)	1.44 (0.48)	2.32 (0.31)	1.74 (0.41)
Ln(L)	2.46 (0.29)	0.08 (0.95)		3.04 (0.21)	1.25 (0.53)	1.12 (0.56)	12.69* (0.00)
Ln(WR)	2.81 (0.24)	5.57** (0.06)	5.23* (0.07)		20.09 (0.00)	1.81 (0.40)	6.44* (0.03)
Ln(M2)	4.88** (0.08)	0.38 (0.82)	1.94 (0.37)	2.11 (0.34)		3.47 (0.17)	1.27 (0.52)
Ln(FDI)	10.60* (0.00)	5.21** (0.07)	1.46 (0.48)	5.10* (0.07)	13.79* (0.00)		1.92 (0.38)
Ln(TECEDU)	0.11 (0.94)	0.39 (0.81)	0.64 (0.72)	5.97** (0.05)	0.95 (0.62)	2.63 (0.26)	

Values in the Parentheses are p values, * , ** has been used to mention the level of significance at 5% and 10%

5. Conclusion and Policy recommendations

This research work has analyzed the impact of workers' remittances along with gross fixed capital formation, Employed labour force, money supply, foreign direct investment and Technical education on GDP of Pakistan from 1973-2013. Most of the studies in literature explain positive impact along with positive association between economic growth and remittances in context of Pakistan . ARDL bound testing approach has been used for empirical analysis. The technique quantifies existence of long-run relationship of outcome variable and independent variables. During analysis it has been observed that there exists long-run relationship between dependent variable GDP of Pakistan and independent variables workers' remittances, GFCF, L, M2, FDI and TECEDU. ECM estimated that the model will adjust towards the long-run equilibrium from short-run disturbance with the speed of 56% per year. CUSUM and CUSUM square which are Structural stability tests also indicate that the model is stable for the longer period of time. From results we also found that foreign direct investment and money supply, technical education and employed labour force also have significant and positive impact on the GDP of Pakistan. Gross fixed capital formation has positive but insignificant impact on GDP of Pakistan. Education which is enrollment in technical institutes also has positive and significant impact on GDP of Pakistan. In order to boost the economic growth of Pakistan Workers' remittances are very important and significant determinant as it is estimated in this study. Foreign reserves can be increased by enhancing the workers' remittances. By considering theoretical and empirical discussion and estimation of this study we have reached to this point that workers' remittances, Money supply and foreign direct investment, Technical education are significant factors which are contributing in the economic growth and prosperity of Pakistan.

Workers' remittances are important and largest source of foreign capital and these are considered boon of the economy. Workers' remittances positively affect the economic growth of Pakistan and also very important element of Balance of payment. Jointly inflow of workers' remittances and foreign direct

investment are source of enhancement for the economic activities in Pakistan. For foreign direct investment we need to set necessary platform for foreign investors and give them full protection.

- Results of this study suggest that migration of workers from poor countries is of great worth and beneficial for the developing countries like Pakistan.
- Due to workers' remittances not only GDP per capita income has been increased but also the standard of living of poor households who receives remittances is improved.
- Workers' remittances can be increased if transaction cost of transferring the workers' remittances is reduced.
- Government should develop such policies which should be helpful in increasing the volume of workers' remittances. Government should motivate the senders of remittances that they should sent remittances through State bank of Pakistan or through government authorized channels.
- Workers' remittances should be utilized in an efficient way so that economic growth of country should increase as there is positive impact of workers' remittances on economic growth.
- Workers' remittances can be utilized for research and development and we can also use it to build physical capital for the country which can be helpful in long run.
- Government should formulate the educational policies in such way that quality of education should improve which could be utilized for the economic growth of Pakistan. Technical Education is source of skilled workers so technical education can play vital role in absorption of foreign imported technology which may be in the form of foreign direct investment as well.
- If Government emphasize on educational policies which are quality oriented then we not only fulfill domestic demand of skilled labor but also we can send our skilled labor to other countries which can become a greater source of remittances.
- Workers' remittances also helpful in maintaining stable exchange rate which is very much important regarding foreign debt if there are more workers' remittances then our exchange rate will improve and our currency will appreciate. Exchange rate appreciation is helpful in reduction of country's foreign debt burden.
- Technical institutions should be established more and government should also promote technical education through proper advertisement to create interest among the students about technical education. Current study suggests that technical education has positive and significant impact so government should give preference to technical education.
- As money supply (M2) has significantly positive impact on Pakistan' economic growth, when we quantify it by GDP and it is cause of decrease in interest rate so government should develop such policies which should be stable regarding supply of money.
- Increased money supply is also important for domestic investment which can reduce the unemployment of the country. Healthy money supply policy by SBP is also helpful in maintaining inflation within limits.
- For further research, researcher can make comparison of the top five receivers of workers' remittances in Asia.

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